

Property design of extruded magnesium-gadolinium alloys through machine learning

Björn Wiese^{a,*}, Sven Berger^{b,1}, Jan Bohlen^c, Maria Nienaber^c, Daniel Höche^b

^a Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon, Institute of Metallic Biomaterials, Functional Magnesium Materials, Max-Planck-Straße 1, 21502 Geesthacht, Germany

^b Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon, Institute of Surface Science, Interface Modelling, Max-Planck-Straße 1, 21502 Geesthacht, Germany

^c Helmholtz-Zentrum hereon, Institute of Material and Process Design, Material Design, Max-Planck-Straße 1, 21502 Geesthacht, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence, Machine learning
Property correlation
Material design
Magnesium alloys
Extrusions

ABSTRACTS

Advanced machine learning (ML) techniques can be used to enable fast processes in evaluation, determination of new correlations, and optimization for material design. In this work, we show how a ML-based model can relate the properties (grain size, tensile yield stress, compressible yield stress, ultimate tensile strength, ultimate compressible strength, compressive and tensile strain under failure, hardness and texture) of indirectly extruded Mg-Gd alloys and the process parameters (extrusion velocity and temperature) with the alloy content of Gd between 0 % and 10 %. An ensemble based approach using shallow artificial neural networks was chosen to predict the material properties. A hyper parameter optimization process was used to obtain the lowest error. This machine learning approach allows defining objective functions to predict, among other factors, the anisotropic behaviour of Mg-Gd or the strengths. It is demonstrated how accurately the trained network predicts isotropic extruded alloys and process parameters, with the results checked against validation data. Validation data was obtained by uniaxial tensile and compression testing as well as optical microscopy of the extruded Mg-Gd alloys and is included. The ML based model is overall slightly better in predicting the material properties compared to a linear-regression approach. This approach allows a prediction of the relationship between process parameters, alloy content and properties in the development of this alloy system or comparable Mg systems. In the future, it will be possible to reduce the number of attempts needed to achieve a specific result or even for online quality monitoring. This approach is promising and needs to be evaluated for other systems with further data.

1. Introduction

Advanced machine learning (ML) techniques offer the possibility to enable fast processes in evaluation, determination of new correlations [1,2] and optimization [3]. Therefore, the existing tools must be adapted, or new tools must be developed for new material design approaches.

The key to sustainable and accelerated materials research lies in the effective use of all currently available research results by, for example, using data-based models by using ML-based techniques, which allow to gain a new insight by even using old research results in large datasets [4]. This enables the effective use of ever more scarce experimental research resources by allowing design of experiment methods to be used, for example, based on ML-based modelling [5] or statistical modelling [6].

Using ML-based models to predict material properties is one of the applications mentioned by Wei et al. [4], while artificial neural networks (ANN) are mentioned as a common technique in material science. Many of the more advanced ML techniques mentioned [4,7] requires a larger set of data points. Especially, limiting ourselves to one material system of Mg-Gd alloys eliminates a lot of the techniques as well as the number of independent parameters given here by the Gd concentration, extrusion temperature and velocity does not require to weight features or enable deep learning approaches. Random forest and extreme gradient boosting based approaches though are, for example, applicable and have also shown good predictive power for limited datasets [4,7]. Ultimately, the best approach cannot be chosen a priori, and a comparison of these different approaches was not part of this work. In the work by Mi et al. [8] a machine learning approach was used to reverse design of Mg-Mn-Al-Zn-Ca alloys in which ANNs showed a high accuracy

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: bjorn.wiese@hereon.de (B. Wiese).

¹ These authors contributed equally.

to predict the material properties of the resulting alloys. While this work has a similar approach it especially shows the power of the seven times larger dataset. Multiple previous studies [9,10] have compared linear regression and ANNs to predict properties of metal materials, with the conclusion that ANNs can outperform regression-based methods such as linear, polynomial or multivariate regression.

Mg-Gd alloys are a well-known Mg alloy system with promising properties for structural lightweight applications [11–13] and biological-medical applications [13–19]. Thermomechanical processing, such as extrusion or rolling, of Mg results in a pronounced texture [20], which leads to an anisotropic mechanical behaviour, and this can reduce with rare earth (RE) elements [21,22]. During thermomechanical processing RE element modify the texture of Mg alloys by promoting non-basal slip [23]. The RE elements and thus in interaction with the process parameters change the texture to the RE texture [24,25], which is one of the efficient ways to improve the formability of wrought Mg products.

Therefore, this Mg-Gd alloy system was used for the present study due to the wide range of applications and the possibilities to produce semi-finished products as profiles by extrusion. The comprehensive parameter study by Harmuth et al. [13] was used as a basis, as it provides a consistent database. The aim of this approach is to obtain a prediction of the relationship between process parameters, alloy content and properties in the design of this alloy system and to transfer this to other comparable Mg systems in the future. Due to the strong texture formation in thermomechanical processes such as extrusion, it is difficult to predict the anisotropic behaviour of Mg and its alloys. To this end, this model provides an estimate of the anisotropy to optimise the properties for uniaxial or multiaxial loading cases. The use for quality monitoring in the industrial production chain is a promising long-term goal of this activities.

2. Experimental

The experimental description of the cast and the indirect extrusion process is published in Harmuth et al. [13] and Wiese et al. [26]. The 26 parameter sets and data sets are taken from Harmuth et al. [13] for Mg-Gd alloys and three from Wiese et al. [26] for pure Mg (Table S1). To extend the range of parameters and properties, other materials were produced as shown in Table 2. The alloying, pouring, solidification, solution heat treatment only for the Mg-Gd alloys and extrusion processes are identical to the above-mentioned publications. The solution heat treatment (525 °C/8 h) and the extrusion temperatures were chosen so that the intermetallic phase Mg₅Gd does not precipitate during the process. Prior to extrusion, the ingot was heated to the respective extrusion temperature for 1 h. All new Mg-Gd alloys are made from pure Mg (99.98 %, MAGONTEC, Sydney, Australia) and Gd (99.9 %, Dr. Ihme GmbH, Berlin, Germany).

The microstructures were examined on the extruded specimens, which were embedded in cold-curing resin parallel to the extrusion direction. Demotec 30 (Demotec Metallography, Nidderau, Germany), as the embedding resin, was mixed in a weight ratio of 10 parts powder to seven parts liquid. All samples were ground with silicon carbide papers up to a grit size of 2500, then polished with 3 µm diamond suspension (Schmitz-Metallographie GmbH, Herzogenrath, Germany) and finally polished with 1 µm SiO₂ oxide polishing suspension (OPS) (Schmitz-Metallographie GmbH, Herzogenrath, Germany) and some diamond suspension of 1.0 µm (Schmitz-Metallographie GmbH, Herzogenrath, Germany). The polished surfaces were cleaned with water and ethanol and dried with a hot air. Etching was done for approximately 3–10 s in a picric acid solution containing 20 ML distilled water, 200 ML ethanol, 7 ML acetic acid and 15–20 g picric acid, followed by cleaning with ethanol and drying with hot air.

Optical microscopy of the extruded samples was used to characterize the microstructures. The analyses were performed with an OLYMPUS GX 53 optical light microscope (OM Digital Solutions GmbH, Hamburg,

Germany). The grain sizes (GS) were determined by using a line intersection method with grain boundaries implemented in OLYMPUS Stream (OM Digital Solutions GmbH, Hamburg, Germany) as the mean value of three images per sample.

The textures of all materials in this work were measured to determine the crystallographic orientations. Six pole figures were measured on polished cross-sections in extrusion direction of the extruded bars. The X-ray diffraction setup and the goniometer setup (Malvern PANalytical, Kassel, Germany) with a Cu K α radiation, a beam size of 1.5 mm \times 1 mm and tilt angles from 0° to 70° were used. Texture evaluation is performed by the open-source codes MTEX [27]. The texture was evaluated using the maximum intensities [m.r.d.] of the back-calculated pole figures for {0001}, {10 $\bar{1}$ 0} and {10 $\bar{1}$ 2}.

Uniaxial tensile and compression tests were carried out at room temperature to characterize the properties along the extrusion direction. Five samples per load direction and material were tested. According to ISO 6892 Form B, the tensile specimens were made with a diameter of 5 mm and a gauge length of 25 mm. The compression tests were performed on compression specimens with a diameter of 8 mm and a length of 15 mm. The universal testing machine Zwick Z050 (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany) with a constant initial strain rate of 10⁻³ s⁻¹ was used for these tests.

The EmcoTest M1C 010 (Salzburg, Austria) machine was used to determine the hardness according to ISO 6507–1 using the EmcoTest M41Eht v4.20.8.0 software from Osterer (Jacksonville, FL, USA). The Vickers hardness was determined with a load of 5 kg and the dwell time of 30 s. At least 10 measurement points were carried out on each material.

3. Machine-learning approach

An often-used neuronal network architecture for regression tasks is a single layer feedforward network, which was implemented using PyTorch v1.13 [28]. Resulting the following setup, a ML network with a linear input layer including bias, a single linear hidden layer including bias, the “LeakyReLU” activation function, a normalization layer using “LayerNorm” and a linear output layer including bias (see Table 1). The process parameter space of Gd concentration, extrusion temperature and extrusion speed have been used as the independent variables x .

Since the training data set only contains 33 samples, additional data points were generated by introducing a uniformly distributed noise. The generation of these additional points was determined by an optimization procedure in which a single neuronal network was optimized regarding the mean squared error (MSE) of the training data (TD), while the individual optimization ranges were determined by the gradient of the MSE and rounded to the next number that is evenly divisible by 5. This approach was applied to optimise the noise level between 0.5 % and 10.0 % in 0.5 % steps. Additionally, the number of generated samples as multiples of the original samples was optimized between 0 and 20, resulting in an optimal noise level of 2 % with 2 additional noisy samples for each experimental sample.

Table 1

Network architecture with y being the output of the layer, x the input of the layer, A the coefficients of the layer, b the bias of the layer.

Input layer size	3 = [Gd concentration, Extrusion temperature, Extrusion speed]
Input layer type	$y = Ax + b$
Size of hidden layer	12
Hidden layer type	$y = Ax + b$
Activation function	$x = \max(0,x) + \text{negative_slope} * \min(0,x)$
Normalization layer	see [29]
Output layer size	1
Output layer type	$y = Ax + b$
Ensemble size	20

Hyper parameter tuning was performed for the number of training epochs with tested numbers being 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000, 10,000 and 20,000, learning rates between $1e^{-3}$ and $1e^{-6}$, the hidden layer size which was optimized in the range of multiples of the input layer size between one and six. These ranges were determined from multiple runs of the tuning procedure and choosing a representative number of point. The lowest MSE for the TD was reached for 2000 epochs with a learning rate of $1e^{-4}$ and a hidden layer size thrice the input layer size. In the work for example by García-Martino et al. [9] ANNs were used as well to predict the tensile yield strength (TYS) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS). They used a similar ANN based approach, without ensemble averaging, with a smaller hidden layer size, but a larger number of input parameters. Resulting in a good prediction of the TYS and UTS.

For the optimization of the network an adaptive gradient descent approach was used called AdamW [30], while the summed absolute error was used as the loss function. To improve the predictive power and reliability ensemble averaging was used. A technique that combines the predictions of multiple machine learning models to obtain a more accurate and robust estimate of the target variable. Ensemble averaging can be applied to regression tasks, where the goal is to predict a continuous value based on some input features. The main idea behind ensemble averaging is that different models may capture different aspects of the data or have different strengths and weaknesses, and by averaging their predictions, one can reduce the variance and bias of the individual models. In this study ensemble averaging was used with an ensemble size of 20. Each of these 20 models was trained with the TD with one sample being removed and individually generated noisy samples. Models of the ensemble with a loss value of higher than 150 % of the mean loss value for the trained output property were not used for the material property prediction and were only used to calculate the variance of the property prediction.

4. Results

The experimental results are summarized in Table 2. In the case of the two new parameter sets for pure Mg, it can be observed that the grain size increases with an increase in the extrusion speed and the strengths and hardness decrease. Thereby the elongation at break decreases in the tensile test (ϵ_T) while it increases in the compression test (ϵ_C). For the textures, there is only an increase in the maximum intensity for the basal component $\{0001\}$ and minimal changes for the other component compared with the published results of Wiese et al. [20] (Table S1).

Table 2

Experimental results from the present work. T is the temperature of the block as well as the container during extrusion and v is the extrusion speed relative to the punch. Collection of all input as training data (TD) and validation data (VD) used in this work are in Table S1.

	Gd	T	v	Grain size	TYS	UTS	ϵ_T	CYS	UCS	ϵ_C	Hardness	Max. texture component intensity [m.r.d.]			Used as	Sample ID
												{0001}	{10 $\bar{1}$ 0}	{10 $\bar{1}$ 2}		
	[wt %]	[°C]	[mm/s]	[μ m]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[%]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[%]	[HV05]					
Mg	0.00	350	3.5	32.8	87	179	7.5	54	292	14.2	28.4	4.6	3.5	3.8	VD	34
	0.00	460	3.5	81.5	70	165	6.4	42	277	15.0	25.9	4.9	2.5	2.9	VD	35
Mg-2Gd	1.78	350	1.9	10.0	93	176	44.1	95	438	33.8	43.3	2.2	1.8	1.6	VD	36
	1.78	460	4.0	46.2	104	173	23.5	74	328	24.4	35.5	2.4	2.2	2.7	VD	37
Mg-4Gd	4.43	460	0.9	21.8	135	205	16.2	114	377	23.5	50.1	2.8	5.8	2.0	VD	38
Mg-7Gd	7.28	400	0.6	7.1	165	246	23.2	164	397	18.0	69.3	3.4	9.8	2.5	TD	21
	7.28	400	1.1	11.3	129	228	28.2	142	390	21.2	67.7	1.8	4.0	1.5	VD	39
	7.28	400	2.2	18.8	110	219	31.0	121	383	24.2	63.1	2.1	1.4	1.5	VD	40
	7.28	400	4.4	29.4	99	211	30.9	110	373	23.0	61.9	3.1	1.7	1.7	VD	41
	7.28	400	6.6	37.7	99	208	30.2	109	370	23.1	60.9	2.3	1.7	1.7	TD	22
	8.80	400	2.2	14.5	153	261	28.2	159	433	17.2	77.7	2.1	1.4	1.7	TD	23
Mg-9Gd	8.80	400	4.4	35.0	119	235	26.1	139	404	17.1	74.9	2.9	1.4	1.7	VD	42
	8.80	400	6.6	39.7	108	228	26.9	122	394	15.9	73.9	3.8	1.6	1.5	TD	24
Mg-10Gd	9.91	350	0.1	2.1	263	308	16.0	264	443	9.7	81.8	3.9	1.4	3.3	VD	43
	9.91	400	2.2	20.7	128	235	26.4	135	434	19.4	68.2	2.0	1.5	1.5	VD	44

In the group of Mg-2Gd, the new data shows a lower Gd content than the material of Harmuth et al. [8] (Table S1). Furthermore, the properties of Mg-2Gd extruded at 350 °C at 1.9 mm/s and 2.2 mm/s show almost similar values, only the ϵ_T as well as the hardness is lower and ϵ_C is higher with lower Gd content. The parameter with the highest temperature and speed results in the largest grain size and the lowest hardness. The strengths are in a comparable range to extrusion at 450 °C with 2.2 mm/s, only the texture component $\{10\bar{1}2\}$ shows a slight increase in maximum intensity. As reported by Harmuth et al. [8], no precipitates of the Mg₅Gd phases could be determined in the microstructure of all Mg-Gd materials in this work.

Mg-4Gd achieves strengths and hardnesses between Mg-2Gd and Mg-5Gd at 450 °C with extrusion speed at 0.6 and 1.1 mm/s. The maximum values of texture, grain size and elongation at break (ϵ_T and ϵ_C) for Mg-4Gd are between those of the other two alloys extruded at 0.6 and 1.1 mm/s.

The complementary results on the Mg-7Gd materials reveals a clear trend: with the reduction of the extrusion speed, YS, US and hardness increase and the grain size decreases. For elongation at break in tension and compression, the mean speed 2.2 mm/s reaches the highest values. The experimental values are in good agreement with the prediction of the ensemble average composed from 20 individual ANNs, as shown in Fig. 1. There, the model predicts even higher elongation at break between extrusion speeds of 1.1 and 2.2 mm/s. Furthermore, the individual results from the ANNs, shown in Fig. 1 in light grey, show that the tensile elongation is much more predictable compared to the compressible elongation at higher velocities, which can be seen from the lower variation. If one compares this further with Fig. 7b, which overall shows good predictive power for compressible elongation this indicates that the learning parameters probably lead to an overfit for compressible elongation.

The maximum textures decrease sharply with the increase of the extrusion speed up to 2.2 mm/s and with a further increase in speed the changes in texture are only marginal.

For the Mg-9Gd materials, an increase in extrusion speed results in an increase in YTS, UTS and grain size, as well as a decrease in hardness, YCS and UCS. The maximum intensity of the texture for $\{0001\}$ increases with the extrusion speed and the other two components are not significantly affected. Compared to low Gd contents at 2.2 mm/s and 400 °C, the strength and hardness increase.

At 350 °C and a reduction from 0.6 mm/s to 0.1 mm/s in Mg-10Gd, the grain size, UCS, ϵ_C and hardness decrease and all other values increase. The comparison between the new and literature values for Mg-

Fig. 1. a) Tensile elongation at break and b) compressible elongation at break based on ML over the extrusion speed for Mg-7Gd (7.28 wt% Gd) at 400 °C. The blue line shows the ensemble average that is composed from the individual light grey models.

10Gd at 2.2 mm/s and 400 °C show higher Gd contents for the new results. The properties are broadly comparable, but the material with less Gd has higher values for CYS, hardness, texture intensity of $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ and $\{10\bar{1}2\}$ and lower ε_T and UCS.

The materials with the manufacturing parameters in Table 3 were selected based on the results of the ML model without ensemble generation and trained only on the validation dataset, which should predict isotropic behaviour between compression CYS and tension TYS. This is the case when $CYS = TYS$ or the ratio of $TYS/CYS = 1$. Which was verified for the Mg-10Gd material by experimental result and for Mg-2Gd at 1.9 mm/s and 350 °C it is also in good agreement. In the case of the pure Mg material and the Mg-2Gd at 4.0 mm/s and 460 °C, this goal of agreement between experiment and prediction is broadly good, but not so for the pure Mg material. For Mg-4Gd at 0.9 mm/s and 460 °C, the prediction of a TYS/CYS of 1 was not confirmed by the experimental results. Hence, the modelling approach was switched to an ensemble model, which yields much better results. The ensemble model trained on the same dataset correctly predicts the values for pure Mg, Mg-2Gd and Mg-10Gd material. While the prediction for the Mg-4Gd material is both incorrect and shows low standard deviation, which indicates a too low variance in the ensemble training process. But instead of predicting the value of 2 samples correctly the ensemble model is able to predict 5 of the experimental validation samples.

Overall, the prediction is in good agreement with the experiment. In the application of predicting the ratio of TYS/CYS in this system to approximately 1, this model allows the possibility to create material-properties to process-parameters maps like the one shown in Fig. 2. This blue tit-like diagram shows what combination of Gd content and extrusion speed will result in a ratio of $TYS/CYS = 1 \pm 0.025$ (and an ensemble standard deviation $2\sigma < 0.03$). This is an example of how this model can be used to predict the material properties over a wide range of process parameters.

Another way to learn from the results is illustrated in Figs. 3–5.

Fig. 2. Map showing process parameters for which isotropic behaviour ($TYS/CYS=1$) is predicted by the ML model with $2\sigma < 0.03$ and $TYS/CYS = 1 \pm 0.025$.

Further property and manufacturing relationship of this kind are possible.

In the prediction in Fig. 3, pure Mg shows the smallest grain sizes at high and low temperatures. The grain size continues to increase and reaches the maximum at the highest extrusion speed and the lowest

Table 3

Compilation of the result for verifying the prediction of the isotropic behaviour (TYS/CYS) using the ML model. Experimental Mechanical (exp. mech.) and estimate from the machine learning (ML) model including error estimate based on double of the ensemble standard deviation.

	Gd [wt%]	T [°C]	v [mm/s]	TYS [MPa]	CYS [MPa]	Exp. mech. TYS/CYS [dimensionless]	Ensemble model TYS/CYS [dimensionless]
Pure Mg	0	350	3.5	87	54	1.61	1.56 ± 0.18
Pure Mg	0	460	3.5	70	42	1.67	1.75 ± 0.40
Mg-2Gd	1.78	350	1.9	93	95	0.98	1.04 ± 0.08
Mg-2Gd	1.78	460	4	104	74	1.41	1.36 ± 0.28
Mg-4Gd	4.43	460	0.9	135	114	1.18	0.99 ± 0.04
Mg-10Gd	9.91	350	0.1	263	264	1.00	0.99 ± 0.04

Fig. 3. Effect of extrusion temperature and extrusion speed from 0 to 15 wt% Gd in Mg on the grain size.

temperature. This trend changes with more Gd in the Mg and leads to an increase in grain size from the lowest extrusion speeds and temperatures to the highest values.

In the case of the prediction for TYS (Fig. 4), there is no continuous trend for pure Mg and with more Gd in the Mg a smooth trend is obtained. The comparable and high strength at low temperature and speed drops sharply as the process parameters increase. This drop in TYS becomes increasingly smaller with more Gd and does not reach a plateau as observed at low Gd content. Fig. 5.

A change in trend could be identified at the ε_T in Fig. 5. For all compositions, the highest ε is predicted at the lowest velocities. Thereby, the maximum ε are at temperatures between approx. 350–400 °C.

To judge the quality of the prediction of the ML model from a mathematical point of view, it was compared to a linear regression of 2nd degree polynomials, which is the polynomial degree resulting in the lowest MSE for this data set. Fig. 6 visualises the basic data set of this

neural network with the training and validation data in comparison. In this case, each sub image shows the input parameters from the manufacturing or input layers.

5. Discussion

For pure Mg, the experimental results are consistent with the findings on the microstructural evolution of extruded Mg or other metals. As the extrusion speed or temperature increases, the grain size increases and the strength and hardness decrease. The temperature during the extrusion process increases more with increasing speed due to the internal friction in the material, which increases the growth of the grains. Larger grains result in a smaller contribution of fine grain strengthening in this material. The more pronounced difference in ε_T and ε_C is also related to recrystallization and can be linked to the texture results. An increase in the basal component $\{0001\}$ increases the contribution of

Fig. 4. Effect of extrusion temperature and extrusion speed from 0 to 15 wt% Gd in Mg on the TYS.

twinning as a deformation mechanism in this load case of the compression test, as described in previous work [26,31].

The extrusion temperature is in the same range as in the earlier work, where no Mg₅Gd precipitation was observed [13,14]. Due to the rapid cooling of the thin profiles in air, out of the solubility range of Gd in Mg, precipitation processes are not possible. A contribution to strength by precipitation in this binary Mg-Gd system can therefore also be excluded in this study. As described in other studies [13,14,22], Gd dissolved in Mg leads to an increase in strength and hardness.

The values for Mg-2Gd from this study are similar to those of Harmuth et al. [8]. The small difference between 1.9 and 2.2 mm/s at 350 °C results in similar dynamic and static recrystallization, and the small difference in Gd content has no significant effect on strength. However, a higher Gd content in the material increases the hardness and the difference in elongation at break may indicate slight changes in texture or activation of other slip systems by the Gd atom in the Mg

crystal [21,32,33]. As already mentioned for pure Mg, the increase in temperature to 460 °C and extrusion speed of 4.0 mm/s leads to a coarsening of the microstructure. Even if the grain size doubles (24.6–46.2 μm), the effect of fine grain strengthening according to Hall-Petch is coupled via $d^{-1/2}$ ($0.20\text{--}0.15\ \mu\text{m}^{-1/2}$) and therefore not as pronounced as with small grains ($13\ \mu\text{m} = 0.28\ \mu\text{m}^{-1/2}$). Therefore, the deviations in the strengths are negligible considering an accuracy of ± 5 MPa in the tensile and compression test.

The correlation of grain size and alloy content on hardness and strength can be explained as before for Mg-4Gd, Mg-5Gd, Mg-7Gd, Mg-9Gd and Mg-10Gd. In general, a trend towards a decrease in the maximum intensity of the texture as well as an inflection of stress between YTS and YCT with increasing Gd content can be observed. This has already been discussed in more detail in the work of Harmuth et al. [8], which showed the combined effect of an enhancement of slip planes and a change in texture in the presence of Gd in the Mg crystal, causing a

Fig. 5. Effect of extrusion temperature and extrusion speed from 0 to 15 wt% Gd in Mg on the ϵ_T .

change in deformation mechanics. Furthermore, the influence of the manufacturing parameters on the mechanical properties becomes smaller with more Gd in the materials.

The change in deformation mechanics can be seen in the present study for the series on Mg-7Gd. In this case, the YTS decreases faster than the YCT and reduces YTS/YCS from 1.01 to ~ 0.91 , as was also shown in Harmuth et al. [8]. In addition, the texture showed a strong change from a high intensity for $\{0001\}$ and even stronger intensity for $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ to a dominated texture component $\{0001\}$ with identical values of the other two textures. A strong basal texture with high $\{0001\}$ intensity is known to lead to isotropic mechanical properties [31] and the texture for $\{10\bar{1}0\}$ is known to be non-recrystallized grains in Mg. Non-recrystallized crystals have a higher defect density and, in the case of Mg, more twins can be expected, which leads to a decrease in ϵ and increases the strength. At the same time the maximum ϵ in both loading

cases is at the extrusion speed of 2.2 mm/s. This was also obtained in this previous work [8], but in the Mg-10Gd material extruded at 450 °C. In that case, the material has the highest ϵ_t value at the extrusion speed of 0.6 mm/s and the highest ϵ_c value at 1.1 mm/s. This shows that the Gd content alone is not important for the YS and deformation behaviour, but that the texture and grain size must also be considered in combination, as these two microstructural features have different effects.

Due to the complex metal-physical relationships detailed models are expensive and complex to use, ML based methods can be used on (existent) measurement data to improve material property predictions in an efficient and cheap way. In doing so, they could help to discover new relationships and offer starting points for developing new physical interpretations.

One of the largest discrepancies in the MSE between the ML model and the linear regression are obtained for the tensile yield stress as

Fig. 6. Histogram of the number of data points plotted over parameters a) extrusion speed, b) Gd content and c) temperature used in the training dataset (TD) and validation dataset (VD).

shown in Fig. 7. The red line indicates the chosen high variance cut-off for which results were assumed to be unreliable. While the green line indicates the data points from the test data set (VD). Although the 2nd

degree polynomial showed the lowest MSE for the linear regression it can be seen that the error overall is quite high, which means the tensile yield stress for Mg-Gd alloys does not show a particularly good

Fig. 7. Comparison of the squared error between the linear regression of the 2nd order polynomial with the ensemble ML model for the a) tensile yield strength, b) compressible elongation, c) compressible yield strength and d) grain size across all the samples.

agreement with polynomial behaviour, but can be accurately described by the presented ML model. While predictions outside of the training data set are on average better for the ML model, especially with the elimination of points with high variance (shown in the figure as the redline). The variance is not a good indication of the error nor is the performance reliably improved over the linear regression approach. This result can be further extended to compressible elongation (Fig. 7), compressible yield stress (Fig. 7), grain size (Fig. 7), texture (Fig. 8) and yield ratio (Fig. 9) of the Mg-Gd alloys, which do not agree very well with the polynomial linear regression but agree very well with the ML model.

Overall better performance is shown in a single material property the tensile elongation (Fig. 10), which is predicted with a lower error for all of the samples.

One of the material properties of the Mg-Gd alloys, ultimate compressible strength shown in Fig. 11 does not agree very well with either model, which might indicate an error in the data set or insufficient description by the currently used process parameters and material properties. Some of the samples show especially high errors, which needs further investigation.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the squared error between the linear regression of the 2nd order polynomial with the ensemble ML model for the texture planes a) {0001}, b) {10 $\bar{1}2$ } and c) {10 $\bar{1}0$ } across all the samples.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the squared error between the linear regression of the 2nd order polynomial with the ensemble ML model for the yield ratio across all the samples.

Fig. 10. Comparison of the squared error between the linear regression of the 2nd order polynomial with the ensemble ML model for the tensile yield strength across all the samples.

Fig. 11. Comparison of the squared error between the linear regression of the 2nd order polynomial with the ensemble ML model for the ultimate compressible strength across all the samples.

Overall, it can be seen from the MSE that the ML based model shows better predictive power compared to the linear regression. For the samples where the prediction does not fit very well neither method is able to predict the material property accurately or reliably. The prediction of extreme values at the boundary of data sets used for training the ML method has a higher uncertainty. For example, pure Mg has the lowest Gd concentration in these data sets and at the same time only two measurements with the same extrusion speed were used for training. The predictive power of ML based approaches is limited by the amount of available data. Therefore, using just the data set that provided in this study this approach does not provide a huge improvement over linear

regression methods to predict material properties outside of the available data range. Which is a similar result to the work by García-Martino et al. [9] in which ANNs did only outperform regression-based methods in some of the cases.

Another influence affecting data consistency is that extruded pure Mg behaves differently from Mg alloy systems containing RE such as Gd. As mentioned in the introduction, RE change the recrystallization behaviour during these thermo-mechanical processes and consequently the texture [24,25].

In Fig. 3, the prediction for grain size agrees with the increase in grain size with increasing speed and temperature in the extrusion process for the alloys. For pure Mg, the two minima do not agree with the metal physical behaviour during recrystallization, but the trend for the alloys is good. The growth rate is higher in the initial phase of recrystallization and decreases as the grain size becomes larger, which can be attributed to the speed and temperature.

The change in YTS can be seen in relation to the grain size development (Fig. 4). For pure Mg, due to the limited data, a discontinuity in the trend can be seen, which is no longer present in the alloys. From the point of view of metaphysics, high strength at low temperatures and speed in the process makes sense because the available energy does not allow complete recrystallization. As more energy is introduced by the speed and temperature, the YTS decreases due to small portions of work hardening and grain-boundary strengthening. The plateau at the different Gd contents can be attributed to the Hall-Petch relationship and the small change in grain size (Fig. 3) at higher temperatures and speed.

The predicted change in ϵ_T (Fig. 5) is also an effect of recrystallization and following grain growth. In the process of recrystallization, the defects in the crystal are removed, which increases the deformability of the metal. After this process is completed, grain growth takes place and larger grains in the material lead to a lower deformability. These opposing processes can be represented with this model in a first approximation.

The experimental results of the Mg-7Gd materials and the prediction support this statement and also show that this applies to the elongation at break in compression. Experimentally, the maximum elongation at break in tension and compression was found to be at 2.2 mm/s, while the prediction of the ML model was between 1.1 and 2.2 mm/s (Fig. 1). Therefore, this model gives a suggestion on how these properties could be improved in interaction, which is otherwise difficult for an anisotropic material like Mg. For solid solution strengthening, a certain content of alloying additions must be achieved in order to increase the critical shear stress in the hexagonal Mg crystal or to achieve continuous behaviour, as has been shown for some alloying elements like Li and Zn [34,35]. The effect in thin solutions or very low-alloy systems cannot be clearly captured by ML approaches because this effect is not continuous. One way to overcome the problem is to collect more data at lower concentrations or not to consider the pure elements in such an approach. However, as shown in the Fig. 4, solid solution strengthening is also reflected in the system.

A map such as the one in Fig. 2 can be used to select specific parameters and properties to reduce the number of attempts and achieve an optimal property profile. The imported step is to define the right function for the targeted property profile. Further applications could be the prediction of such material properties as strength, grain size, texture etc. as a function of the parameters.

6. Outlook

The current results show that using the current data set it is not possible to predict reliably outside of the measured process parameter space. Further, optimization of the training process and combining the ensemble model with different modelling approaches such as extremely randomized trees, which also show good results for sparse data sets. Moreover, statistical analysis might yield a more accurate description of

the prediction reliability than the ensemble standard deviation. The data set in this work is rather small. However, it could be shown that it can help to select process parameters more specifically for material design. Furthermore, this work shows that more data is needed to improve the prediction quality of this type of ML tool. We plan to collect a larger dataset of Mg based alloys to allow also for the prediction of alloy composition by adding a structure descriptor to the ML model. As well as to increase the predictive power to a larger production property space. After sufficient validation, this tool could also be used in the industrial sector for quality monitoring along the production chain. Furthermore we plan to investigate design of experiment approaches in our future work and take into account both statistical and ML-based approaches.

7. Conclusion

Using machine learning techniques, we developed an ensemble model generation method that accurately predicts material properties after manufacturing steps within the measured process parameter space. The method used outperformed linear regression in terms of prediction accuracy. Without an underlying metal-physical model, the predictions correspond with the experiments and the metal-physical explanation for the change in properties to a first approximation. Therefore, the method has the potential to design material properties for the final product within a given range of process parameters. However, we also found that the method had limited predictive power outside of the measured process parameter space.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Björn Wiese: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Sven Berger:** Methodology, Investigation, Software, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Jan Bohlen:** Conceptualization, Validation. **Maria Nienaber:** Validation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Daniel Höche:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Competing interests

All authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Data Availability

The raw data and the training code can be found in the Zenodo publication with the doi [10.5281/zenodo.7695823](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7695823).

Acknowledgments

This research is part of the OpenModel project which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 953167.

The authors thank Jochen Harmuth for providing the unpublished data of Mg-7Gd and Mg-9Gd and for his permission to use them in this article.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.106566](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2023.106566).

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